

D8.3

Ethical Issues Report

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D8.3

Ethical Issues Report

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Partner short names

TUB	(Technische Universität Berlin)
UNITELMA	(Università degli studi Unitelma di Roma)
UNI	(Ente Italiano di Normazione)
AUA	(Geoniko Panepistimion Athinon)
USC	(Universidad de Santiago de Compostela)
APRE	(Agenzia per la promozione della Ricerca Europea)
NOVA	(Nova - Institut für politische und Ökologische Innovation GMBH)
BAM	(Bundesanstalt für Materialforschung und Prüfung)
RSB	(Roundtable on Sustainable Biomaterials Association)
ISEAL	(ISEAL Alliance)

Abbreviation

GDRP: General Data Protection Regulation

GA: Grant Agreement

DMP: Data Management Plan

PP: Privacy Policy

CP: Cookie Policy

1 Executive Summary

This report (Deliverable 8.3) provides a general overview of the ethical issues associated with the implementation of the STAR4BBS project. It describes how ethical issues and data protection requirements are addressed in the different activities, to comply with the highest standards of research ethics and integrity, and with the EU, national and international law. In particular, the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights, and the ethical standards and guidelines of Horizon EUROPE 2020 (Horizon Europe regulation 2021/695) are rigorously applied, regardless of the country in which the research is carried out. All participant institutions are required to comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and EU Directive 95/46/EC on Data Protection. The key aspects covered in this report refer to: Methodology; data protection (see D8.2) Consent Form and Information Sheet (fully detailed in the annexes to this deliverable); Data Anonymization; Gender Issues.

2 Introduction

This report provides a general overview of the ethical issues associated within the implementation of STAR4BBS project. It presents the actions taken or to be taken within the project to ensure compliance with the highest ethical standards and the applicable EU, international and national law on ethical principles. It describes how ethical issues and data protection requirements are addressed in the different activities, to comply with the highest standards, in particular, the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights, and the ethical standards and guidelines of Horizon EUROPE 2020 (Horizon Europe regulation 2021/695), European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, and Ethics for Researchers – Facilitating Research Excellence in FP7. All participant institutions are required to comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and EU Directive 95/46/EC on Data Protection.

The ethics and legal compliance objectives cover transparency, consent, and monitoring of risks. The identified data protection and privacy objectives address the fundamental principles of fair and lawful processing, quality of data, and limitation of storage duration, as well as data confidentiality and integrity. Finally, the communication of results objective addresses requirements specific to dissemination results as required by European funding programs.

In particular, this deliverable aims at providing: a) detailed information on the informed consent procedures that will be implemented for the participation of humans in project activities, in particular for stakeholders involved in the co-creation workshops and other project events; b) templates of the informed consent forms and information sheet.

3 Methodology

In order to guarantee the compliance with basic ethical (research) standards, the STAR4BBS consortium discussed – on multiple occasions – the ways in which this issue can be addressed. Making use of the extensive research experience and considerable background with ethics of the various research centers which comprise part of the consortium, the STAR4BBS team was able to outline different actions.

3.1 Identification of core ethical requirements for the execution of the project (self-evaluation)

The purpose of this action was to identify the European ethical values that are at the core of the project: what is the benefit that it aims to achieve, who could be affected positively or negatively, and what are the trade-offs that might occur (including conflicts of ethical values). All members of the Consortium were sent a basic research-ethics self-evaluation. If any of these questions were answered with ‘yes’, the Consortium agreed to further discuss this issue at the STAR4BBS Kick-Off meeting. The Consortium’s expectation with regard to the different research projects in the Work Packages was that, none of the issues posed in the self-evaluation would be relevant, or pose an ethical risk in the research. However, in order for all the members of the Consortium to be aware of ethical risks, the Consortium deemed it worthwhile and valuable to take the time to consider these issues. These first assessments were conducted during proposal preparation and grant agreement preparation. As indicated in the Ethics and Self-assessment chapter of the Grant Agreement (GA), in particular in the Table of Ethics Issues (page 131 of the GA), no major ethical issues apply to the STAR4BBS project.

In order to identify core ethical requirements, relevant legislations, strategies and EU guidelines have been consulted, including: the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights, the General Data Protection Regulation. Non-legislative policy and guidance documents have also been considered, such as the FP7 Data protection and privacy ethical guidelines, the Opinion of the European Group on Ethics in Science and New Technologies on the ethical implications of new health technologies and citizen participation, and the Declaration of Helsinki on ethical principles for medical research involving human subjects. Other relevant texts may need to be identified and consulted during the project’s initiation.

In order to ensure coordination and consistency among partners, guidelines and templates were provided to partners.

3.2 Data protection

To consider the ethical questions associated with the extensive stakeholder engagement in the project, a well-defined methodology for data collection and data treatment will be developed and will be Included in the Initial Data Management Plan (DMP) (Deliverable 8.2, due in Month 6). The DMP will be main targeted on data protection related to the project activities, the project results and achievements. More specifically, the plan will include information on: (i) what data will be collected, processed and/or generated; (ii) which methodology and standards will be applied; (iii) whether data will be shared/made open access; and (iv) how data will be handled and preserved (including after the end of the project). UNIT will ensure that collected data will strictly comply with the Regulation (EU) 2016/6791 - the European Union's new General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). plan will be developed following the recommendation provided by the EC and the Horizon Europe template for the DMP.

3.3 Stakeholder engagement exercise

Since the beginning of the project, APRE conducted a stakeholder mapping exercise, that will convey in a detail stakeholders' engagement guidelines to be shared among the partners (D6.1 due in Month 5). To proceed with the implementation of this task (under WP6, led by APRE), APRE created a dedicated from (Annex 4), shared among all the network already developed in previous EU projects (e.g. STARProBio) in which partners were involved, and will also draw on the broad networks and knowledge of project partners and associate partners. Due to the Data Protection Policy adopted by the European Commission, APRE studied a dedicated Privacy Policy [PP] (Annex 5) in order to provide to each subscriber a clear Regulation about the use and purpose of the data collected. This PP will be available, as the Cookie Policy [CP] on the website. All the information and historic changes about this issue will be available in D6.1 by Month 5. As defined at the end of the STAR4BBS subscription form, data is collected following EU GDPR [Article 6.1.a and 6.1.f].

3.3.1 Stakeholder engagement: aim and future activities

Stakeholder engagement will involve several tools, among others: in-depth interviews, surveys and questionnaires, and will follow several routes. Stakeholders will be involved and invited in future activities, such as workshops, webinars, focus groups, as defined in T6.2.

In line with the GDPR and Privacy Policy adopted by the project, the consent procedures for recruiting/contacting participants for co-creation workshops, in-depth interviews, workshops, webinars, focus groups, surveys and questionnaires will follow the standard practices and protocols of the research organizations in each country in which a case study will be carried out. In all cases these practices will satisfy all requirements as laid down by the EU in the Horizon 2020 Programme.

4 Consent form and Information sheet

This section includes detailed information on the informed consent procedures that will be implemented for the participation to the events organized by STAR4BBS. It also includes templates of the informed consent forms and information sheet, to be used in order to ensure that activities of the STAR4BBS project apply in compliance with Regulation (EU) 2016/679 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data (General Data Protection Regulation or GDPR).

Each participant will be contacted via e-mail and asked if he/she would be interested in participating in the event proposed. If the participant agrees, he/she will be asked to sign a digital Consent Form (Annex 3 for participation in events/meetings/workshops or Annex 1 in case of Interview/survey/questionnaires) before participating. The consent form, to be signed every time for every event by the participants, will be provided to them at least a week before the event, hence allowing sufficient time to examining it before participating. The form will provide details on how the information collected will be used, linked to the Privacy Policy (PP) of the project. Engaged users will be also provided with an Information Sheet on the research (Annex 2). If users agree to the terms indicated in the Consent Form, they will proceed to fill in the survey/questionnaire and/or participate in the workshop/interview/webinar/focus group DPM framework (general data protection regulation). This procedure will be applied both for face-to-face and virtual meetings.

4.1 Link between the Ethical Report and the Data Management Plan

By signing the Grant Agreement, the beneficiaries committed to respect basic EU values (such as respect for human dignity, freedom, democracy, equality, the rule of law and human rights, including the rights of minorities).

Data Management Plan (D8.2) and a deliverable on ethical issues (D8.3) are foreseen. They are strictly linked. The Ethical requirements will be considered for the development and application of DMP, mainly concerning the personal data protection and the GDPR Application.

Data collection (mainly for stakeholder engagement activities and workshops) will be compliant with GDPR. Before collecting any data, the person involved will be informed through an informed consent explaining the project and the use of the data, collection, storage and cancellation. The presence of associated partners does not represent an issue regarding the collection of data, since GDPR legislation applies to the UK and Switzerland too.

Compliance with ethical principles and applicable international, EU and national law in the implementation of research activities not originally envisaged (or not described in detail) in the DoA will be ensured. Any ethical concerns raised by those activities will be handled following rigorously the recommendations provided in the European Commission Ethics Self-Assessment Guidelines.

5 Data anonymization

In general terms, STAR4BBS will focus on the participants' views related to the effectiveness and robustness of certification schemes, labels and related standards, and policy related to bio-based product issues, collecting non-personal information. Sensitive issues will be carefully avoided and, if any personal information is given, researchers will ensure that the opinions cannot be directly associated to individuals.

In general, individual names will not be identified in the research. In the specific case of interviews, the minutes of each of them, will not mention names, but will be labelled with an identifying code to allow easier consultation of documents. If individuals agree to be quoted, researchers will first verify the accuracy of quotes that will be used with the interviewee.

6 Gender Issues

As for gender issues, all participant institutions are required to follow the H2020 Programme "Guidance on Gender Equality in Horizon 2020" and with any updates it might receive during the lifetime of the project. STAR4BBS will ensure gender balance: in the stakeholders' identification process; in all initiatives and activities of the project; at all levels of personnel assigned to the action, including supervisory and managerial level.

7 Annexes

7.1 Annex 1: Informed consent form

The 'Informed Consent Form' reported hereafter is a template prepared for stakeholders' interviews to be adapted for other types of stakeholders' interactions.

<p style="text-align: center;">Informed consent form Project STAR4BBS - 101060588</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Sustainability Transition Assessment Rules for Bio-Based Systems</p> <p>I consent to participate in the European Union-funded¹ STAR4BBS research project led by the Technische Universität Berlin (TUB). I am aware that the purpose of this research is to support the European Commission in the full implementation of European policy initiatives, including the Green Deal, the European Bioeconomy Strategy, the Circular Economy Action Plan, and all European policy instruments which contribute and support the transition towards sustainable bio-based systems. The research will furthermore be disseminated more widely, e.g. in academic papers, briefing papers, media etc.</p> <p>This research will involve an interview lasting up to 1 hour where I will be invited to discuss my knowledge about this area with particular reference to the experience of my organisation.</p> <p>I understand that I am participating in this research voluntarily and that I am free to terminate the interview at any time. I am also aware that I am free to refuse to answer any questions that I feel are commercially or institutionally sensitive or relate to topics that I do not wish to discuss. I understand that I have the right to ask questions and receive understandable answers before making any decision.</p> <p>I understand that I will only be asked to provide professional, not personal, information and that if I wish, the record of my involvement in the research will be kept confidential. I have been informed that everything I say will be anonymous and if I wish, I can remain anonymous in future published material. The interview data will be recorded via paper notes/tape recorder and I understand that I can request a copy of the notes/transcript to review if I wish. I understand that I am also allowed to delete or make any changes to the notes/transcript if I feel my answers could be improved or clarified. I understand that this research will be used to develop indicators and a new monitoring system for assessing the effectiveness and robustness of existing international and EU SCS, B2B labels, and related traceability systems applicable to biological feedstock and bio-based materials and products.</p> <p>I understand that should the research team consider making the anonymised data from this interview available by open access I will be contacted for a second informed consent regarding this step.</p> <p>I understand that this research conforms to European Commission guidelines and the requirements for research data management of Horizon Europe. Finally, I have been given the contact details of the research team and I have been informed that I am free to contact the Project Coordinator or any other member representing the project about any queries relating to my data or the project itself.</p>
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¹ Grant agreement no. 101060588 — STAR4BBS — HORIZON-CL6-2021-ZEROPOLLUTION-01

7.2 Annex 2: Information sheet form

Information Sheet form - Project STAR4BBS - Grant Agreement Number 101060588

Sustainability Transition Assessment Rules for Bio-Based Systems

STAR4BBS supports the European Commission in the full implementation of European policy initiatives, such as the Green Deal, the European Bioeconomy Strategy, the Circular Economy Action Plan, and all related European policy instruments dealing with bioeconomy, sustainability and certification schemes which contribute and support the transition towards sustainable bio-based systems.

STAR4BBS project does so by developing sustainability Transition Assessment Rules for bio-based Systems, which include indicators and a new monitoring system for assessing the effectiveness and robustness of existing international and EU SCS, B2B labels, and related traceability systems applicable to biological feedstock and bio-based materials and products. The overall aim of STAR4BBS is to maximize the potential of Sustainability Certification Schemes (SCS) and labels to support a successful transition to sustainable bio-based economy.

STAR4BBS will involve important stakeholders (including scheme owners, policy makers, and industry) in the design of research and the monitoring system and in the development of practical recommendations emerging from the research and analysis to ensure that the project achieves its ultimate goal. In particular, an increased uptake of the most effective SCS and labels by the bio-based industry will support the development of circular, climate-neutral, sustainable biobased systems that will mitigate climate change, increase resource efficiency, preserve and restore ecosystems, biodiversity, natural resources, and the quality of air, water and soil.

The specific objectives of STAR4BBS are to:

- Gain a precise picture of existing international and EU SCS and labels both for biological feedstocks and bio- based materials and products, as well existing monitoring systems;
- Gather specific global trade data and information on volumes of biological feedstock and bio-based materials and products, differentiating between certified and uncertified flows;
- Explore the impact and contribution of existing SCS and labels to enabling sustainability and also the impact on the adoption of SCS and labels on market access and trade within bio-based systems, and to what extent sustainability SCS and labels are a catalyst or barrier;
- Identify relevant and feasible indicators, related metrics and minimum sustainability and traceability requirements for inclusion in the monitoring system;
- Develop a fit-for-purpose monitoring system to assess the effectiveness and robustness of existing SCS and labels in supporting achievement of sustainability targets and enabling transparent traceability in global trade flows;
- Assess the effectiveness and robustness of reviewed SCS and labels by applying the monitoring system;
- Evaluate overall costs and benefits from adopting the reviewed SCS and labels in selected value chains and performing a feasibility study on B2B labels best-performing from either environmental or social aspects;
- Maximize both the relevance and the uptake of the project findings and recommendations involving a broad range of stakeholder

The STAR4BBS consortium includes as partners:

- Technische Universität Berlin, Germany (TUB) (Consortium leader)
- Università degli Studi di Roma UnitelmaSapienza, Italy (UNITELMA)
- Agricultural University of Athens, Greece (AUA)
- Universidad de Santiago de Compostela, Spain (USC)

- Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea, Italy (APRE)
- Nova-Institut für politische und ökologische Innovation GmbH, Germany (NOVA)

As affiliated entity:

- Ente italiano di Normazione, Italy (UNI)

As associated partners:

- ISEAL Alliance, United Kingdom (ISEAL)
- Bundesanstalt für Materialforschung und -prüfung, Germany (BAM)
- Roundtable on Sustainable Biomaterials, Switzerland (RSB)

STAR4BBS receives funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2021-2027) under grant agreement no. 101060588, Topic HORIZON-CL6-2021-ZEROPOLLUTION-01-07 - International and EU sustainability certification schemes for bio-based systems.

Additional information can be found here: www.star4bbs.eu

7.3 Annex 3: Informed Consent Form for Processing Personal Data, Photographs, videos and recorded speeches/interviews collected in the course of STAR4BBS Project events/meetings/workshops

Data protection notice and declaration of consent – Processing of your Personal Data, Photographs, Videos and recorded speeches/interviews collected in the course of your participation to the event **[INSERT NAME OF EVENT]** in **[PLACE – DATA]** as speaker (art. 13 of the Regulation (UE) 2016/679 (General Data Protection Regulation or GDPR)).

DATA CONTROLLER

[INSERT NAME INSTITUTION WHICH ORGANIZES THE EVENT] – **[INSERT ADDRESS, NUMBER, CITY, NATION]** - VAT: **[XXXXXXX]**- FISCAL CODE: **[XXXXXXXXX]** ; e-mail **[INSERT EMAIL of THE PERSON IN CHARGE FOR DATA CONTROLLING]** .

PERSONAL DATA UNDERGOING PROCESSING

Name, surname and professional role, picture and voice referred to you.

PURPOSE AND LAWFULNESS OF PROCESSING

STAR4BBS Project Consortium will process photographs and video recording collected in the course of the event in order to document its success stories and promote its own projects and activities. To these purposes, it might incorporate the aforementioned material, also partially, into its institutional communications, such as multimedia products, brochure or dissemination via STAR4BBS website or social media pages. Due to your role in the event, the material collected can include personal data referred to you.

The processing of your personal data may be carried out only with your consent, as established by Art. 6 Para. 1 Letter a) GDPR; your consent can be granted by filling out and signing the consent declaration box below.

Please note that is not subject to consent the use of general photographs and video in which the natural persons are not immediately identifiable.

CONSEQUENCES OF THE FAILURE TO PROVIDE PERSONAL DATA

The provision of your personal data is not mandatory; if you don't consent to the processing, we will not be able to collect, publish and disseminate any material in which your personal data are included.

You may withdraw your consent with effect for the future at any time, addressing the request to STAR4BBS at the contacts above. The withdrawal of consent shall not affect the lawfulness of data processing based on consent before its withdrawal.

CATEGORIES OF RECIPIENTS OF THE PERSONAL DATA

Personal data shall be communicated to the following categories of recipients:

- Supplier in charge of managing STAR4BBS web site
- Social media Platform used by STAR4BBS project and related PPs;
- Supplier that, on behalf of STAR4BBS project, perform production and editing activities, such as video, web and digital agency.
- **[ADD other possible categories]**

TRANSFERS OF PERSONAL DATA TO THIRD COUNTRIES

Your personal data are processed by STAR4BBS Consortium within the European Union, but they can be transferred to countries outside the EU, in particular to the USA, where the provider of the social media Platform used by STAR4BBS project (i.e. Facebook, YouTube, Twitter) are established.

STORAGE PERIOD OF PERSONAL DATA

Your personal data are deleted as soon as the purpose for which they were collected has ceased to exist, or if you have withdrawn your consent to data processing.

RIGHTS OF THE INTERESTED PARTY

You have the right to request and receive, at any time, information on your personal data being processed by STAR4BBS Project Consortium and to request their rectification.

Where applicable, you also have the right to request the erasure or the restriction of processing of your personal data, to object to their processing at any time and to receive your personal data in a structured, commonly used and machine-readable format; moreover, you have the right to lodge a complaint with the competent supervisory authority as per art. 77 GDPR.

7.4 Annex 4: STAR4BBS Database subscription form

This form was created and managed by APRE, task leader of T6.1 “Mapping stakeholders and developing procedures for engagement”. All the information related to the implementation and outputs of this task are reported in D6.1 “STAR4BBS Stakeholder map” (due to M5).

STAR4BBS Database Subscription | Join our community!

The overall aim of the STAR4BBS, a three-year EU funded project, is to **maximize the potential of Sustainability Certification Schemes (SCS) and B2B labels to support a successful transition to sustainable bio-based economy**. At the core of the STAR4BBS project is the development of indicators and a new monitoring system for assessing the effectiveness and robustness of existing international and EU SCS, B2B labels, and related traceability systems applicable to biological feedstock and bio-based materials and products. This information will create the foundations to support achieving the much-needed harmonization between schemes and transparency in global and EU trade flows.

Through the developed new monitoring system, existing SCS and labels will be analyzed, and the results, as well as additional research on certified and uncertified trade flows and on the impacts of costs and benefits of certification schemes and labels, will substantially increase understanding of the potential of these schemes to contribute to policy and industry sustainability goals and will build awareness of the differences between the schemes. The project will involve important stakeholders (including scheme owners, policy makers, and industry actors) in validation of the concept and the design of the monitoring system and in the development of practical recommendations emerging from the research and analysis to ensure that the project achieves its ultimate goal. An increased uptake of the most effective SCS and labels by the bio-based industry will support the development of circular, climate-neutral, sustainable biobased systems that will mitigate climate change, increase resource efficiency, preserve and restore ecosystems, biodiversity, natural resources, and the quality of air, water and soil.

This consent form is designed to collect expressions of interest to be part of STAR4BBS Stakeholders Database, projects financed by the European Commission. All the data collected shall not be used outside STAR4BBS activities and will be processed following the EU GDPR [article 6.1.a and 6.1.f] and STAR4BBS Privacy Policy [go to <https://star4bbs.eu/>]

By subscribing this form, you will receive:

- Invitation to project-related events, especially the co-creation workshops planned for 2023
- News of relevant activities and initiatives implemented in the context of bioeconomy-related EU projects in which STAR4BBS consortium is involved
- Project Newsletters (released every 5 months)

For further information, please contact Dr. Luana Ladu (TUB), project coordinator:

luana.ladu@tu-berlin.de

CORDIS page of STAR4BBS: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101060588>

1. Name *

2. Surname *

3. Organization *

4. Organization website *

5. Country *

6. e-mail *

7. Category *

- Certification schemes owners
- Academia / Research organization
- Industry
- Policymaker / Public institution
- Civil society
- NGO
- Association (e.g. consumers, employers' organization)
- Altro

8. The information you will send will be stored and processed through email only for the purpose of receiving information about the activities and events of the project. The data you will submit will be used by STAR4BBS. STAR4BBS will treat your personal information with all the confidentiality and security in accordance with the established data protection regulations. You may withdraw your consent to use the data at any time, by sending an email to: star4bbs@apre.it *

- I agree

Questo contenuto non è stato creato né approvato da Microsoft. I dati che invii verranno recapitati al

7.5 Annex 5: STAR4BBS Privacy Policy

This Privacy Policy was developed by APRE in the framework of the implementation of T6.1 “Stakeholders mapping” and the development of the website.

PRIVACY NOTICE PURSUANT TO ARTICLE 13 OF REGULATION (EU) 2016/679

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)

The information is given in compliance with article 13 of Regulation (EU) 2016/679 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data (General Data Protection Regulation or GDPR) to individuals interested in receiving news, information, invitations to events and workshops, publications, announcements and newsletters relating to the activities conducted by STAR4BBS, managed by APRE (mail to star4bbs@apre.it).

Definitions

“Personal data” (article 4, paragraph 1 of the GDPR) means any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person (‘data subject’); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person.

“Processing” (article 4, paragraph 2 of the GDPR) means any operation or set of operations which is performed on personal data or on sets of personal data, whether or not by automated means, such as collection, recording, organization, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure or destruction.

Data Controller

For the purposes of the GDPR (article 24) the Data Controller is:

APRE – Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea,
via Cavour 71 – 00184 Rome – Italy
e-mail segreteria@apre.it
Tel +39 6 48939993

Type of data processed

As part of our activities, APRE collect and use personal data provided by you, the data subject, e.g. name, surname, email, organization to the extent that is needed and helpful to attain the purposes set out below.

Purpose of processing and profiling

We may collect and use personal data for the following purposes:

- Applications, registrations, access and administrative management of Users;

- Communication and promotion of the activities of the project e.g. news, information, invitations to events and workshops, publications, announcements and newsletters via e-mail; as well as analysis and research;

Enabling the Service Provider to address and handle claims or litigations.

Personal data may be collected also for profiling purposes (off by default). Specifically, we may ask you to give information about your areas of interest so that you receive communications that are targeted to your preferences.

You can change your preferences at any time.

Legal basis for processing personal data

For the purposes set out above, the legal basis of processing is the consent you, the data subject, give to the processing of your personal data, [article 6.1.a) of the GDPR].

and for the legitimate interest of the Service Provider (i.e. security monitoring) [article 6.1.f) of the GDPR]

Data Subject Rights

In relation to your personal data you can exercise your rights as data subject under the GDPR, namely:

- Right of access [article 15 of the GDPR];
- Right to rectification [article 16 of the GDPR];
- Right to erasure ('right to be forgotten') [article 17 of the GDPR];
- Right to restriction of processing [article 18 of the GDPR];
- Right to data portability [article 20 of the GDPR];
- Right to object [article 21 of the GDPR].

You have the right to withdraw your consent at any time.

The rights set out above can be exercised in writing by sending an email to star4bbs@apre.it.

You as data subject have also the right to lodge a complaint with the Italian Data Protection Authority (*Garante per la protezione dei dati personali*).

For further information about data subjects rights visit our website www.star4bbs.eu.

Data retention

Your personal data will be kept until the date of withdrawal of consent. Any longer storage periods remain unaffected, in the event that they are required due to legal, accounting and/or fiscal obligations.

After the storage period, as described above, the data you have provided will be erased.

Consent to data processing

You are free to give or withhold your consent to processing of your personal data for the purposes above. We need your freely given consent to send you news, information, invitations to events and workshops, publications, announcements and newsletters regarding our activities. Should you deny your consent, we will be unable to send you said communications.

Disclosure of data outside of the APRE

We may disclose your personal data outside of our Association for specific reasons. In particular, your personal data may be made available to entities providing IT system management on behalf of our Association, competent authorities and/or public bodies, European Commission, and supervisory authorities to comply with statutory requirements. Where appropriate, we shall formally appoint said third parties Data Processors pursuant to article 28 of the GDPR.

How data is processed

Your data will be processed our controller's employees and other authorized individuals. Said employees, and other authorized individuals may consult, use, process, compare the data as well as carry out any other appropriate action, including using automated means, always in compliance with statutory requirements that ensure, inter alia, protection of the confidentiality and security of the personal data, as well as data accuracy, update and appropriateness to the purposes for which the data is collected and used, as stated above.

Transfer of data outside of the EU

Your Data will not be transferred outside the European Union.

Changes and updates

APRE may make changes and/or additions to this privacy notice including as a result of regulatory changes.

General Information about cookies

Definition of "cookies". Cookies are short fragments of text (letters and/or numbers) that allow the web server to store in regard to the client (the browser, e.g. Internet Explorer, Chrome, Firefox, Opera, etc.) information to be reused during visits to the site (session cookies) or later, even after days (persistent cookies). Cookies are stored, according to user preferences, by the single browser on the specific device used (computer, tablet, etc.).

Based on the characteristics and use of cookies, various types of cookies can be distinguished:

Technical cookies strictly necessary. These cookies are essential for the proper functioning of a website that are used to manage various services related to websites (for example, logins or access to the reserved functions in the sites). The duration of cookies is strictly limited to the work session. Deactivation of strictly necessary cookies may compromise the user experience and navigation of the website.

Purposes of the processing and purposes of technical session cookies. The cookies used on the Site are for the sole purpose of performing computer authentication or the monitoring of sessions and the storage of specific technical information concerning users accessing the servers of the Data Controller that manages the Site. In this view, some activities on the Website cannot be performed without the use of cookies, which in such cases are therefore technically necessary.

CONSENT REQUEST PURSUANT TO ARTICLE 6 OF THE GDPR

By clicking on the "[Sign up](#)" button in the subscription form you give your consent to our processing of your personal data in accordance with the purposes described above.

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“ Sustainable bio-based systems through effective certification & labelling ”

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